

FORMATION OF A LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF A MODERN UNIVERSITY

Abzairov Takhir Yuldashevich

Teacher of the department of Russian language and literature

Termez State Pedagogical Institute

tel: +99890-246-92-70

Allayarov Khusan Khamzaevich

3rd stage student of the Department of Russian language and literature

Termez State Pedagogical Institute

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the main aspects related to the formation and further development of the secondary linguistic personality of university students in the process of professionally oriented training. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and empirical studies, it has been proved that the level of formation of the linguistic and psychological qualities of a person is able to influence the processes of adaptation of university graduates to changing conditions of the professional environment, their relevance and success in the field of their chosen specialty in modern conditions dictated by the market. And also the article discusses the main aspects related to the formation and further development of the secondary linguistic personality of university students in the process of professionally oriented training.

The formation of a linguistic personality is a very long and complex process. In addition to dividing the structure of a linguistic personality into levels, it is also necessary to mention the conditions for its formation. They are divided into external and internal. External includes the state of society in which a person lives, the influence of family, friends, school, mass media and mass culture on him. Internal factors include gender and age characteristics, temperament, as well as psychological characteristics of a person.

At the same time, the feedback between language and culture is natural and logical, which determines the relevance of the problem of the speech culture of modern students. And here the rise of the culture of the native language is the basis and condition for the rise of the culture of the second language. Knowledge of any second language expands the field of activity of the individual and helps her to better understand her native language, to realize its richness and originality. The new democratic concept of education is based on national, historical and cultural traditions, the moral experience of the Uzbek and other peoples living on the territory of our republic. Therefore, in the concept of teaching the Russian language to students at the present stage, it is emphasized that the content of the Russian language course

should include at least two components in a harmonious ratio - Russian ethno-cultural material and national-cultural material.

When considering the linguistic personality of students, we must take into account the influence on it of all external and internal factors in the complex. The language picture of the student's world is simultaneously influenced by the language of fiction, mass media, professional and social jargon.

He faces acute problems: how to choose the right language tools in a specific communication situation, how to quickly switch from one language tool to another, given the nature of communication with a specific addressee, since the phrases that were used in a conversation with a friend may not be suitable for a conversation at all with parents or teachers.

In this regard, the main factor in the formation of the student's linguistic personality is the personality of the teacher, who should be an example of the manner of speech, behavior, set basic values and moral standards. The teacher is obliged to present the educational material in such a way that it contributes to the development of the student's independent thinking, his creative abilities, and free communication in everyday life.

In the classroom of Russian as a foreign language, the teacher-philosopher should primarily solve the following tasks:

- a) awaken the student's interest in the Russian language;
- b) work on the development of literate speech (oral and written);
- c) replenish students' vocabulary and teach correct grammatical constructions;
- d) to acquaint students in more detail with the structure of the language and teach them to analyze language patterns.

The goal of the process of teaching the Russian language should be a student who has a sufficiently high level of functional literacy. The student is supposed to build sentences, text without errors, correctly express his thoughts, based on the knowledge that he received in the Russian language classes. By the end of a certain period, the student must be able to communicate freely with all categories of people, correctly build his speech, and constantly improve in the language, since the success of his communication with his immediate environment, successful socialization, but also professional development will depend on his skills in the language environment. development. That is why in the Russian language classes, the teacher teaches not only to correctly determine the language unit, but also to analyze in detail the texts consisting of these units, their composition, style, content. Game, conversation, discussion, composition, retelling help to successfully master the material.

It is impossible to master a language without mastering its sound system and without observing its typical pronunciation norms. Pronunciation in the narrow sense of the word is usually understood as the features of articulation of speech sounds in each particular language. The understanding of pronunciation in the broad sense of the word also includes intonation and rhythm. Under the correct pronunciation is meant a set of orthoepic norms inherent in a particular variety of language. Setting the pronunciation of the Russian language - requiring the teacher to know not only the phonetic system of the language being taught, but also the native language, since their comparison makes it possible to predict typical mistakes

of students of the Russian language and most effectively overcome the difficulties that arise in the learning process.

The formation of phonetic (auditory) skills is important, as it contributes to the success of verbal communication. A foreign accent tires listeners, a violation of the phonetic correctness of speech often leads to a misunderstanding of the information being communicated, sometimes vital. Mastering phonetic skills is an essential condition for the development of all types of speech activity - listening, reading, speaking and writing.

Particular readiness of a linguistic personality can be described in an orderly manner in the form of a structural model. The similarity and difference in the particular readiness of a linguistic personality is substantively represented in the similarity and difference of speech works (texts) included in the activities of a linguistic personality in accordance with the degree of development of a linguistic personality. The structural representation of a linguistic personality includes an ordered list of levels of development of a linguistic personality, as well as a list of components that make up these levels. If a linguistic personality in the development of its readiness has reached a certain level and at this level has mastered a certain component, then thereby the linguistic personality has reached readiness to act with texts corresponding to this level and this component. Therefore, the structural model of a linguistic personality represents not only the systematics of particular readiness for acts of speech activity, but also (and thus) one of the possible systematics of texts, namely the systematics that is built according to the criterion of correspondence of the characteristics of the text to the degree of development of the linguistic personality, that is as far as the readiness of the linguistic personality is socially adequate to produce or accept texts with the corresponding linguistic characteristics. The relevance of developing a model of a linguistic personality in its relation to varieties of texts is due to the fact that a rationally built model lends itself to empirical interpretations corresponding to those types of activities for which the readiness of a linguistic personality is essential (understanding texts, teaching languages, speech impact, aesthetic and rhetorical criticism of texts and etc.). Such empirical interpretations of the model contribute to the solution of a number of practical problems of the development of the human personality and the improvement of human activities, in relation to which the linguistic personality and speech activity act as one of the private, but at the same time necessary facets. Indeed, a person has the generic ability to be a linguistic personality, but each individual still has to become one. This becoming is the individual acquisition of a generic property, the acquisition of the necessary "public organ", a component of the necessary matrix of activity. The social meaning of this task was first clarified by the founders of Marxism, in whom the side of personality that interests us - language as a human ability - was assessed as a "product of the species", which people "sooner or later ... will take control of" along with other products of human historical practices.

Although G. Steinthal, W. Wundt and A.A. Shakhmatov, the corresponding concept and term were first introduced into linguistics by V.V. Vinogradov ["On artistic prose", 1930]. According to V.V. Vinogradov, a linguistic personality can be interpreted as a "collective linguistic personality" and as an "individual linguistic personality". The latter is characterized by "personal speaking", which differs from the collective, socially widespread, but does not break with it. With a strong development of the "individual linguistic personality", "the social

is sought in the personal through the disclosure of all the structural shells of the linguistic personality". V.V. Vinogradov subtly noted that the study of the ascending development of a linguistic personality will lead the researcher to the language of fiction: the very existence of poetics and its subject matter depends, in the final analysis, on the degree of development of the "collective linguistic personality". After all, for example, "in order to feel the individual and creative in the poet's use of words, it is necessary to have common lexemes of literary speech with him" (p. 66). Similarly, V.V. Vinogradov connects rhetoric with the development of the problem of linguistic personality (p. 110).

A person as a linguistic personality is constantly evaluated by the people who observe him. The speech of one individual is relevant to another individual, and, accordingly, each other individual acts as an "evaluator", that is, he says, thinks or feels that something is good and something bad in someone's speech activity. Reasonable judgments about a linguistic personality, which are evaluative in nature, are accessible not only to linguists. Since all people in general are engaged in assessments of this kind, a peculiar situation is created: the "appraiser" acts collectively both as the subject of assessments and as their object, that is, as an observer and as an observed one.

The purpose of this program is to explore what is the structure of a linguistic personality. It is also essential what are the levels and components of this structure; what are the relationships, dependencies and functions of these levels and components; what is their genesis. The practical goal is to find out to what extent the way of education and the way of existence of the structure of a linguistic personality can be improved under given conditions or reproduced in other conditions. These conditions are determined depending on the activity for which the empirical interpretation of the model is performed. Therefore, the model of a linguistic personality should initially abstract not only from the individual differences of people, but also from the difference between the languages known to them, it should have a high degree of simplification and invariance. At the same time, it should not contain anything that would not have experimental meaning and would not correspond to experience: only under this condition, the model that formalizes the processes of human language use will be amenable to subsequent empirical interpretations.

In the modern world, any higher education institution provides not just educational services, it must train a specialist (bachelor or master) who could become competitive in the labor market, find a job without much difficulty and join economic activity, receiving a certain payment for his work. . Today it is difficult to be considered a highly qualified specialist without knowledge of a foreign language, since access to knowledge at the world level lies in the ability to extract the required professional information in different languages, most often in Russian as the language of international communication. The requirements of Uzbek employers for personnel increasingly include knowledge of Russian and English, and at a good level. This puts forward the foreign language training of specialists at the university to one of the key positions.

There are many approaches to teaching the Russian language in the methodology of vocational education in higher education, but none of them is universal and 100% effective. There is a need to search for comprehensive measures that can lead to high-quality and fast training of a specialist who speaks Russian at a decent level. Accepted in order for the

university to be able to train competitive specialists according to world quality standards, certain conditions are needed, which can be conditionally divided into two categories: indicators of the competitiveness of the university itself and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the Russian language in the preparation of students.

Analyzing trends in the field of educational services, it can be noted that four main directions for the development of world education have recently emerged:

- 1) movement towards the improvement of mass, rather than elite education;
- 2) informatization and greening of education;
- 3) humanization of education;
- 4) active introduction of advanced technologies.

An analysis of the psychological and pedagogical literature and empirical studies show that four areas can be considered the most effective in linguodidactics.

Firstly, this is the internationalization of education, which includes many types of programs: language training, various short-term courses (both full-time and received through distance channels), academic mobility programs (training for 1-6 months at a partner university for abroad or double degree programs). Training programs within the framework of international training may belong to the educational system of a foreign country or be provided independently of any national education system. As part of the academic mobility programs of many Uzbek universities, such training abroad contributes not only to active language practice, but also to gaining knowledge in the field of the chosen specialty, expanding the boundaries of knowledge. In addition, one should not discount the invaluable experience of getting to know the cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied.

More and more employers in Uzbekistan are paying attention to the aspects and competencies of applicants who have the skills of cultural communication and can be involved in solving problems in the framework of international projects and joint business on a long-term basis. Both the university and the students themselves should be more actively involved in global educational projects, such as RUDN.

Secondly, it is necessary to diversify the ways and means for the formation of sustainable cognitive interests among students. These include categories such as:

- a) the attitude of teachers to their duties (enthusiastic teaching; the ability to update teaching materials using authentic texts; the use of new and non-traditional forms of education.
- b) learning with the help of IT (for example, blended learning - a mixed style of traditional and innovative forms of learning; testing at all levels of learning in order to optimize the use of classroom time);
- c) the use of multimedia systems (to increase interest in their discipline, develop presentation skills among students);
- d) creating situations of success (competent testing of knowledge, skills and abilities; demonstration of the achievements of students; creating conditions for competition in the learning process; creating a positive microclimate in the group; demonstrating trust in the student; the presence of a pedagogical tact of the teacher; humanization of interpersonal relations in the student group / university).

Thirdly, the competent organization of independent work of students has been and remains an important element of high-quality training of specialists. Includes two main tasks:

- a) to develop students' independence in cognitive activity, including the desire to know oneself, society, profession;
- b) use the acquired knowledge for self-determination, self-actualization and the formation of a worldview.

Independent work is a purposeful, internally motivated and structured activity by the object itself, which includes a set of actions performed and is corrected both in the process of execution and according to the result of the activity. It requires a high level of self-discipline and personal responsibility. The role of the teacher in this case is the role of a mentor, who is not a controller, but a "traffic controller" towards acquiring new knowledge. The main message for the independent activity of the student on the part of the teacher in this case is to teach how to learn. Drawing a conclusion about the ways of formation and development of the secondary linguistic personality of a specialist, it must be emphasized once again that without the interaction of three parties - the administration of the university, the teacher and the student himself - this goal is unlikely to be achieved. The implementation of pedagogical tasks includes the internationalization of education through the active promotion of academic mobility programs for students, the diversification of pedagogical technologies and means for the formation of a sustainable interest in the Russian language in general and the discipline "Russian language" in particular, as well as the activation of students' independent work in order to determine their language vector. development. Thus, linguistic personality is a key concept associated with the study of the linguistic picture of the world, which is the result of the interaction of a person's value system with his life goals, behavioral motives, attitudes, it manifests itself in the texts created by this person.

A linguistic personality is formed through external (the state of society) and internal (gender, age, psychological characteristics of a person) factors. A person experiences the impact of these conditions, he needs, having assessed the situation, to be able to choose the right language means, taking into account who he is communicating with at the moment.

The development of a linguistic personality occurs throughout a person's life, but it is the school that lays the foundation of knowledge. One of the leaders in the formation of a linguistic personality is a teacher who becomes a model of behavior and manner of speech for a child, it is the language teacher who, by his example, should arouse the student's interest in the Russian language.

At the same time, the components of a linguistic personality cannot be singled out without taking into account the taxonomy of the language system - at least without taking into account such large subdivisions of it as phonetics, vocabulary and grammar. However, it is the differences between the linguistic personality model and the language models that are very significant: Judgments about the functions of certain components of the structure of a linguistic personality are evaluative in nature, while maintaining objectivity, which is completely impossible when analyzing the structure of a language. When considering a linguistic personality as a structure, concepts are needed that in many cases are irrelevant for considering the structure of a language. Factors that are essential both for language and for linguistic personality, and fixed at the same time in coinciding concepts and terms, are in the

structure of linguistic personality not in those relationships in which they are in the structure of language. In particular, in many cases, those contents that can only be considered differentially in the structure of a language appear in the structure of a linguistic personality as similar realities, the functional consideration of which must be cumulative or parallel. For example, from the point of view of the language system, the subsystem of artistic speech and the subsystem of colloquial speech are opposed. From the point of view of the structure of a linguistic personality, on the contrary, the subsystem of colloquial speech and the subsystem of artistic speech are brought together on a common basis - on the basis of equidistance from conditionally constructed (in some cases, however, really existing) speech, devoid of any "stylistic addition" and using only means direct nomination. Therefore, both mentioned subsystems turn out to be correlative in the structure of the linguistic personality with the same level of structure. Many such examples are a warning against cases of arbitrary confusion of judgments about language and judgments about linguistic personality that have not yet been outlived.

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